

Influence of Ring Spinning Parameters on the Properties of Hollow Polyester Yarns

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Abstract:

Hollow yarns have been produced to modify the yarn properties and to increase the volume of air entrapped air in the yarn structure. The yarns were produced by introduction of PVA filament in yarn formation zone of ring spinning system. Hollow yarns were obtained after dissolving the PVA core by hot water treatment at 90°C. 80 Ne yarn (7.4 Tex) is used in the core and 0.8 micro denier polyester fiber as a sheath maintaining a 30/70 core/sheath ratio throughout the study. A core spun yarn of 22.7 Tex was produced with three different spinning parameters - core yarn tension, break draft and twist multiplier respectively. The optimal values have been obtained using Box and Behnken Design. It is found that the chosen variables significantly influenced the yarn parameters.

Keywords: break draft, core yarn tension, Hollow yarn, micro-denier polyester, PVA, TM

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1. Introduction

The demand for fabrics made from hollow yarn is ever increasing due to the better wearing comfort of the fabrics. These yarns may be produced through core yarn spinning in a ring frame with a tension device, hollow spindle, open end methods including rotor and friction spinning methods. But the conventional ring spinning technique is the simplest of all. Core spun yarn is produced in ring frame by combining a continuous strand referred as 'core' through the tension rollers and the staple fibres referred as a 'sheath' via the normal drafting line. The core may be a filament or a spun yarn. With a high level of PVA content in the core of hollow cotton yarn, the strength and breaking elongation is more than that of the 100% cotton yarn. Softness and bulkiness of the PVA dissolved hollow cotton yarn is better than that of 100% cotton conventional yarn [1]. Bulky yarns may be produced by enhancing the PVA% without making significant changes to yarn strength [2]. The irregularity in hollow yarns is influenced by the methods of spinning and PVA extraction. It could be minimized by treating the yarn in hot water after fabric formation [3]. Hollow yarns have good extension which can be modified by its yarn structure [4]. The decrease in fibres in the yarn cross section results in improved yarn bulk due to improved air space [5]. Yarn pore size influences the structural, physical, moisture and thermal behaviour of the fabrics. Microscopic views of cut-cross sections are a method to understand the yarn pore size and its distribution [6]. The hollow yarn garments usually look brighter and provide a feel good comfort to the wearer [7]. Fabrics made with hollow weft yarns shows good water

absorbency [8]. The fabrics produced with hollow yarns have better thermal resistance and moisture vapour transmission as compared to 100% regular cotton yarn fabrics [9]. Yarn structure modifications influence comfort property, changing the vapour transmission behaviour of fabrics [5]. Though a good number of research on hollow yarns have been cited, works by considering various spinning parameters to produce yarns with optimized properties are limited. This paper considers the optimization of spinning parameters like core yarn tension, twist multiplier and break draft on yarn characteristics with the aid of Box-Behnken design.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Material

Micro denier polyester fibre with a mean fineness of 0.8 Denier, cut length of 38mm was used to produce a roving of 1.0 hank with 1.2 TPI. The core component was water soluble 80 Ne PVA yarn and resultant count of 22.7 Tex was produced in ring frame. The core yarns were produced in a ring frame with special attachment and the spindle speed was kept at 17500 rpm. A three variable factorial design, proposed by Box-Behnken (Table 1) was used to investigate the main and interaction effects due to the process parameters, that is, core yarn tension, twist multiplier and break draft on dependent variables like yarn tenacity, breaking elongation, unevenness and hairiness. The core spun yarn was wound on perforated cylindrical spool, taking sufficient to avoid yarn entanglements during the extraction of PVA. The cheese packages thus obtained were dipped in boiling water for about 20 minutes, followed by cold water treatment which resulted in the PVA extraction. The samples were then dried and conditioned.

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Table 1 - Coded variables used in production of PET/PVA core yarns

Yarn Parameters	Coded Levels and Values		
	-1	0	+1
Core yarn tension % (X_1)	2.7	3.0	3.3
Break draft (X_2)	1.14	1.2	1.26
Yarn TM (X_3)	3.6	4.0	4.4

Table 2 - Box-Behnken design for three variables

Order	Variables		
	Core yarn tension % (X_1)	Break draft (X_2)	TM (X_3)
1	2.70	1.14	4.00
2	3.30	1.14	4.00
3	2.70	1.26	4.00
4	3.30	1.26	4.00
5	2.70	1.20	3.60
6	3.30	1.20	3.60
7	2.70	1.20	4.40
8	3.30	1.20	4.40
9	3.00	1.14	3.60
10	3.00	1.26	3.60
11	3.00	1.14	4.40
12	3.00	1.26	4.40
13	3.00	1.20	4.00
14	3.00	1.20	4.00
15	3.00	1.20	4.00

2.2 Determination of physical properties of yarn

The details of instrument used, testing standards and the number of samples tested for each yarn characteristics are given in Table 3. All the tests were carried out after

conditioning the samples in standard atmospheric conditions, that is $27.0 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 2\%$.

Table 3 - Particulars of yarn testing

S. No.	Parameters	Equipment used	Standard	Sample size
1	Yarn count	Wrap reel	ASTM D1907-07	030 (03 tests/cop)
2	Single yarn TPI	Electronic Twist Tester	ASTM D1422-99	100 (10 tests/cop)
3	Single yarn strength and elongation	Uster Tensojet 4	ASTM D 2256-02	200 (20 tests/cop)
4	Yarn Evenness, Imperfection and Hairiness Index - H (cm/cm)	Uster - UT4	ASTM D 1425-09 (at 400 m/min for 1 min)	1 test/cop = 10 test

2.3 Statistical Methods

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to study the effect of spinning parameters on the tenacity, breaking elongation, unevenness and hairiness of hollow polyester yarn. The Design Expert Software 8.0.7.1 was used to determine the effect of interactions of spinning parameters on the hollow polyester yarn characteristics. The information available from 3D surface contour diagram explains the interactions between the spinning parameters. Multiple regression equations were arrived to establish the relationship between the spinning parameters and various properties of hollow polyester yarn.

3 Results and Discussions

The physical properties of hollow polyester yarn are given in Table 4. The ANOVA results of hollow yarn properties and the regression equations are listed in Tables 5 and 6 respectively.

Table 4 - Physical properties of Hollow polyester yarn

S.No.	Core Yarn Tension % (A)	Break Draft (B)	Yarn TM (C)	Linear density (Tex) (AD)	Breaking Elongation% (AD)	Tenacity g/tex (AD)	IPI /Km (AD)	U% (AD)	H. Index (AD)
1	2.7	1.14	4	21.6	19.51	9.4	48	10.1	5.1
2	3.3	1.14	4	21.7	19.52	10.1	46	10.4	5.2
3	2.7	1.26	4	21.5	19.43	9.8	44	10.3	4.8
4	3.3	1.26	4	21.8	19.6	9.9	47	10.2	4.5
5	2.7	1.2	3.6	21.6	19.66	9.3	46	10.9	5.8
6	3.3	1.2	3.6	21.5	19.82	10.1	47	10.3	5.7
7	2.7	1.2	4.4	21.8	18.92	10.2	43	9.8	4.4
8	3.3	1.2	4.4	21.6	18.65	10.5	47	10.5	4.2
9	3	1.14	3.6	21.4	20.11	9.2	42	10.8	5.8
10	3	1.26	3.6	21.8	18.72	9.7	47	10.5	4.8
11	3	1.14	4.4	21.7	18.25	10.3	45	9.6	4.2
12	3	1.26	4.4	21.3	18.53	10.1	48	10.4	4.7
13	3	1.2	4	21.4	19.95	9.3	45	10.5	5.3
14	3	1.2	4	21.6	19.53	9.3	49	10.1	5.1
15	3	1.2	4	21.7	19.63	9.5	48	10.3	5.5

AD - After dissolution of PVA Core

Table 5. - ANOVA result of hollow polyester yarn properties

Source	Tenacity		Breaking Elongation		Unevenness		Hairiness Index	
	F-Value	p-Value	F-Value	p-Value	F-Value	p-Value	F-Value	p-Value
Core Yarn Tension	31.44	0.0007*	8.79	0.0138*	6.05	0.0307*	7.47	0.0196*
Break draft	51.08	0.0008*	0.01	0.9183	0.42	0.5434	0.53	0.4976
Yarn TM	3.53	0.1187	2.92	0.1479	1.17	0.3271	4.80	0.0798
AB	110.94	0.0001*	37.23	0.0017*	22.83	0.0050*	45.21	0.0011*
AC	10.188	0.0242*	0.12	0.7415	1.50	0.2739	0.68	0.4459
BC	7.07	0.0449*	0.87	0.3918	15.94	0.0104*	0.04	0.8444
A ²	13.86	0.0137*	13.24	0.0149*	11.41	0.0197*	9.61	0.0268*
B ²	41.91	0.0013*	0.51	0.5044	0.0	1.0000	0.98	0.3663
C ²	5.68	0.0628	5.27	0.0701	0.34	0.5807	4.77	0.0806
Model	48.79	0.0009*	19.45	0.0070*	0.78	0.4165	1.42	0.2869

* p-Value less than 0.05 indicates significant difference

Table 6 - Regression equations for hollow yarn properties

Hollow yarn parameters	Regression equation	R ²
Tenacity	$+9.37+0.24*A+0.063*B+0.35*C-0.15*A*B-0.12*A*C-0.18*B*C+0.32*A^2+0.12*B^2+0.34*C^2$	0.9826
Breaking elongation	$+19.70+8.750E-003*A-0.14*B-0.49*C+0.040*A*B-0.11*A*C+0.42*B*C+0.086*A^2-0.27*B^2-0.53*C^2$	0.9406
Unevenness	$+10.30+0.037*A+0.062*B-0.28*C-0.100*A*B+0.32*A*C+0.28*B*C+0.000*A^2-0.050*B^2+0.075*C^2$	0.9160
Hairiness Index	$+5.30-0.063*A-0.19*B-0.58*C-0.100*A*B-0.025*A*C+0.37*B*C-0.12*A^2-0.27*B^2-0.15*C^2$	0.9308

(A-Core Yarn tension %, B-Break draft, C-Yarn TM)

3.1 Bulkiness & cross section of hollow polyester yarn

The Figures 1 and 2 represent the photographs of longitudinal and cross sectional views of yarn before and after dissolving the PVA. The removal of PVA leading to

hollow central portion is evident in figure 2(b). The hollow spaces are entrapped by air resulting in a slightly bulk appearance as compared to normal yarns as shown in figures 1(a) and 1(b).

1(a)

1(b)

Figure 1- Longitudinal view of yarn captured in LEICA Microscope- 1(a) - Before dissolving PVA; 1(b) - After Dissolving PVA

2(a)

2(b)

**Figure 2 - Cross sectional view of yarn captured in LEICA Microscope
2(a) - Before dissolving PVA; 2(b) - After dissolving PVA**

3.2 Effect of spinning parameters on Tenacity of hollow polyester yarn

Figure 3 - Interaction of spinning parameters of hollow polyester yarn on Tenacity

Figure 3 reveals that the tenacity of hollow polyester yarn is influenced by the chosen parameters. Lower values of core yarn tension, yarn TM and break draft results in lower yarn tenacity. Higher levels of yarn TM and median levels of core yarn tension and break draft are found to improve yarn tenacity. With higher TM levels, the fibres are well bound to the structure and the distortion is less even after the removal of PVA from the core by dissolution.

3.3 Effect of spinning parameters on Breaking Elongation of hollow polyester yarn

Figure 4 - Interaction of spinning parameters of hollow polyester yarn breaking elongation

Figure 4 - Interaction of spinning parameters of hollow polyester yarn breaking elongation

Figure 4 reveals that the breaking elongation of the hollow polyester yarn is influenced by the chosen parameters. Median to higher levels of core yarn tension, yarn TM and break draft results in better breaking elongation. In general, when tenacity values are better at higher levels as discussed in the previous section, fibres are able to sustain higher elongation before breaking, resulting in higher tenacity and breaking elongation values.

3.4 Effect of spinning parameters on Unevenness of hollow polyester yarn

Figure 5 reveals that the unevenness of the hollow polyester yarn is influenced by the chosen parameters. Lower to Median levels of core yarn tension, yarn TM and break draft results in lower unevenness values. The yarns formed at lower break draft values could have resulted in lesser drafting waves which is a reason for reduced unevenness.

Figure 5 - Interaction of spinning parameters of hollow polyester yarn Unevenness

3.5. Effect of spinning parameters on Hairiness of hollow polyester yarn

Figure 6 reveals that the hairiness values of the hollow polyester yarn is influenced by the chosen parameters. With an exception to core yarn tension, the other parameters namely higher levels of yarn TM and break draft results in lower hairiness values. Figure 7 shows the regression plots of observed and predicted values of various yarn properties. The observed model has predicted the properties in a significant way, which is clear from the R values, which are greater than 0.9 for all the plots.

Figure 6 - Interaction of spinning parameters of hollow polyester yarn on Hairiness

Figure 7 - Predicted versus observed values of tenacity, breaking elongation, unevenness and hairiness of hollow polyester yarn

4. Conclusion

The chosen parameters namely, the core yarn tension, yarn TM and break draft were found to influence the yarn property in a significant manner. Higher levels of yarn TM and median levels of core yarn tension and break draft are found to improve yarn tenacity. Median to higher levels of core yarn tension, yarn TM and break draft results in better breaking elongation. Lower to Median levels of core yarn tension,

yarn TM and break draft results in lower unevenness values. Lower levels of yarn TM and break draft results in lower hairiness values. The regression plots gave a good correlation between the observed and predicted values confirming the strong influence of chosen parameters in deciding the yarn property. The Core yarn tension of 2.7%, Break draft of 1.19 and Yarn TM of 4.4 were derived as the optimized values from the Design Expert software.

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